

Appendix C: Pytransit odd and even transit model fits

This section shows the Pytransit models fitted separately to the odd-numbered and even-numbered transits for each candidate. Each chart shows the individual observations (blue), the phase bin mean fluxes (red) and the PyTransit fit (black). The horizontal solid line shows the minimum flux from the full light curve model and the dashed lines shown the associated 1σ uncertainty limits of the minimum flux. The vertical black lines show the boundaries of the transit ingress and egress from the full light curve models.

Fig. 1: Pytransit model fit to Gaia DR3 2100980735718445312 (KIC 4459924) odd-numbered transits (left) and even-numbered transits (right)

Fig. 2: Pytransit model fit to Gaia DR3 2100325529865507712 (KIC 4543171) odd-numbered transits (left) and even-numbered transits (right)

Fig. 3: Pytransit model fit to Gaia DR3 2078315162505745920 (KIC 8175131) odd-numbered transits (left) and even-numbered transits (right)

Fig. 4: Pytransit model fit to Gaia DR3 2126910621514995968 (KIC 8293539) odd-numbered transits (left) and even-numbered transits (right)

Fig. 5: Pytransit model fit to Gaia DR3 2079369937757906688 (KIC 9040849) odd-numbered transits (left) and even-numbered transits (right)

Fig. 6: Pytransit model fit to Gaia DR3 2085335681690420608 (KIC 9674230) odd-numbered transits (left) and even-numbered transits (right)

Fig. 7: Pytransit model fit to Gaia DR3 2128959007378441472 (KIC 11033410) odd-numbered transits (left) and even-numbered transits (right)